

1 **Large area gridded population mapping based on building density, height and type from Earth**
2 **Observation data using census disaggregation and bottom-up estimates**

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11 **Abstract**

12 Gridded population data is widely used to map fine scale population patterns and dynamics to
13 understand associated human-environmental processes for global change research, disaster risk
14 assessment and other domains. This study mapped gridded population across Germany using
15 weighting layers from building density, building height (both from previous studies) and building type
16 datasets, all created from freely available, temporally and globally consistent Copernicus Sentinel-1
17 and Sentinel-2 data. We first produced and validated a nation-wide dataset of predominant residential
18 and non-residential building types. We then examined the impact of different weighting layers from
19 density, type and height on top-down dasymetric mapping quality across scales. We finally performed
20 a nation-wide bottom-up population estimate based on the three datasets. We found that integrating
21 building types into dasymetric mapping is helpful at fine scale, as population is not redistributed to
22 non-residential areas. Building density improved the overall quality of population estimates at all
23 scales compared to using a binary building layer. Most importantly, we found that the combined use of
24 density and height, i.e. volume, considerably increased mapping quality in general and with regard to
25 regional discrepancy by largely eliminating systematic underestimation in dense agglomerations and
26 overestimation in rural areas. We also found that building density, type and volume, together with
27 living floor area per capita, are suitable to produce accurate large-area bottom-up population estimates.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Within the last decades, global population increased rapidly. While 3.0 billion people lived on Earth in
31 1960, this is anticipated to reach approximately 10.0 billion by 2060 [1]. The regional and local
32 dynamics of this global growth are highly diverse and can be traced back to a complex interplay of
33 factors such as economic development and restructuring, urbanization and mobility, social, cultural
34 and political frameworks, medical capacities, conflicts or climate change related effects that all affect
35 either fertility and mortality rates or migration [2]. Data about patterns of human population are
36 essential to understand the relation between those factors and underlying societal or human-
37 environmental processes and are key requirements for international development frameworks such as
38 the Sustainable Development Goals [3] or the United Nations Paris Agreement [4]. Population is a key
39 variable in socio-economic metabolism and sustainability pathway research [5], and population
40 density has recently been proposed as Essential Societal Variable [6].

41 As census data is limited to administrative census units, gridded population approaches are a popular
42 alternative [7]. These redistribute national or regional census population counts to smaller, grid-cell
43 based target units that better represent local population patterns. Gridded population has been used to
44 inform research in several domains, such as climate change and related health research [8–10],
45 quantification of ecosystem services [11], urban development and urbanization patterns [12,13],
46 disaster risk assessment and exposure [14,15] or settlement characterization and categorization [16,17].
47 To date, a wide range of freely accessible global products with varying spatial and temporal resolution
48 have been developed, including the Global Rural-Urban Mapping Project (GRUMPv1, 18,19),
49 Gridded Population of the World (GPWv4.11, 20), the Global Human Settlement Population Layer
50 (GHS-POP, 21,22), LandScan [23,24] or WorldPop (25–27). An overview including global and
51 continental products and their specifications can be found in 7).

52 The redistribution of national census population to smaller grid cells is commonly based on a
53 weighting layer. In an *area-weighted* approach, population is equally redistributed to all land-surface
54 cells, e.g. in GPWv4 [28]. *Dasymetric mapping* techniques refine this procedure by incorporating
55 spatial ancillary data that is presumably related to population presence and density and that affects

56 redistribution weights of each individual cell [29,30]. *Binary* dasymetric approaches redistribute
57 population using one or more ancillary layers that describe presence or absence of populated areas.
58 This can include mask layers such as protected areas, steep slopes or non-built-up land cover types
59 (e.g. in [31]), where population is not expected (*limited* variables, [32]) or data that identify built-up
60 cells that population can be redistributed to. *Weighted* dasymetric approaches account for one or more
61 ancillary datasets assuming that they are unequally related to population density (*related* variables,
62 [32]) and population is redistributed based on a cell-based weight. Weights can directly correspond to
63 ancillary features (e.g. road density can regionally relate directly to population density [33]) or can be
64 derived from ancillary layers with an unknown a-priori relation to population based on modelling. A
65 common way is random forest (RF) modelling, where population density or a weighting response
66 variable is predicted using ancillary data such as land cover information, night-time lights, climatic
67 data, topographic information or vector-based features [26]. This procedure identifies previously
68 unknown relations and can outperform binary dasymetric mapping [31] and are, for example, used in
69 contributions to WorldPop [26]. Hybrid approaches combine a modelled weighting layer within a
70 previously masked settlement area [34].

71 Settlement layers are a key information to map gridded population [34,35]. Over the last years,
72 important advances have been made with regard to mapping settlements on the national to global scale
73 from remote sensing, improving spatial and temporal resolution as well as accuracy [36]. The Global
74 Human Settlement Layer (GHSL, [37]) and the Global Urban Footprint (GUF, [38]), continued by the
75 World Settlement Footprint (WSF, [39]), are among the best-known global products. Research showed
76 that a continuous representation of settlements through density maps is advantageous to further refine
77 gridded population maps [33,40–42], because a densely built-up area can potentially house more
78 people than a same-sized, but less densely built-up area. Currently, however, GHS-POP is the only
79 approach that globally accounts for settlement density, deriving density at 250m spatial resolution
80 from an averaged high-resolution binary layer.

81 Despite these advances and the considerable accomplishments of globally redistributing census
82 population to a grid-cell level, current state-of-the-art research faces four major challenges:

- 83 • **Building type:** Particularly, *de jure* approaches that redistribute population based on the legal
84 place of residence, currently used in most products [7], require a fine representation of where
85 people can permanently live. Even though many global gridded population maps do account
86 for settlements, they do not account for the respective building type. This is, however,
87 essential because population and settlement presence correlate differently in single-family and
88 multi-family areas and do not correlate in industrial and commercial areas. So far, building
89 types have been incorporated only implicitly into population mapping, for example through
90 land use data for covariate modeling [26], or in very local settings [43].
- 91 • **Building height:** Vertical building structure is a highly relevant descriptor of settlement
92 structure in general [36,44] and population in particular [45,46]. As operationalized building
93 height products are only emerging recently, it has not yet been integrated into large-area
94 gridded population maps, even though population is also vertically distributed.
- 95 • **Census data:** Redistributing census population relies on accurate census data in the first place.
96 Dasymetric mapping is impossible when the total population is unknown and difficult when
97 its estimation is outdated or incomplete [7]. The quality, consistency and temporal resolution
98 of census data varies across countries and census data might erroneously be considered
99 accurate [32]. This is particularly important as census information is often used to both
100 redistribute population and to validate the estimation at a finer scale (e.g. 31,34,47), probably
101 resulting in an overestimation of accuracy.
- 102 • **Data consistency and modeling:** The use of modeled weighting layers based on ancillary
103 data can introduce uncertainty based on variations in local data quality. Furthermore, physical
104 relations between population and ancillary data are hard to quantify when weighting layers are
105 derived from RF modeling [7]. Those statistical relations might also be regionally specific and
106 the resolution of available census data can be important when transferring models to regions
107 where they are different [48].

108 As there is a demand for gridded population data in places where administrative census units are large
109 or in countries with quickly increasing population, high migration rates and less frequent or accurate

110 census [7], bottom-up approaches are promising, since they do not require spatially exhaustive census
111 data to estimate gridded population for the entire region. They seem, thus, potentially more robust
112 towards spatially incomplete data or if national census data is outdated. However, bottom-up
113 approaches are rather rare as they rely on detailed survey information or other high-resolution data.
114 This is why, despite the lower cost compared to national census, bottom-up mapping has focused on
115 settings with good data coverage so far [49]. To date, bottom-up population estimates mainly focus on
116 specific demographic phenomena [50] and local to sub-national analyses only [43].

117 The goal of this study was to contribute to an accurate, large area and fine-scale gridded *de jure*
118 population estimate using both census-based dasymetric mapping and a bottom-up approach on a
119 nation-wide scale. We established a workflow that derives population estimates for the year 2018 on a
120 grid cell level and that responds to the identified challenges of current large-area products. We used
121 three covariate layers that provide a direct physical relationship to population without statistical
122 modelling. All layers were derived at 10 x 10 m² spatial resolution from freely available, temporally
123 and globally consistent Copernicus Sentinel-1 A/B and Sentinel-2 A/B (from here S1 and S2) imagery
124 as well as OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, thus, minimising the use of region-specific ancillary covariates.
125 We incorporated (1) a building density layer that quantifies the share of building-covered surface, (2) a
126 building height layer and (3) a layer that indicates the type of buildings including major residential and
127 non-residential types. Those layers were used as an input to both binary and weighted dasymetric
128 mapping as well as a bottom-up approach using literature-guided calculations on living floor area per
129 capita. Our study area was Germany as a) both building density and building height layers were
130 already available and validated for this country and b) accurate census data at different administrative
131 levels and information about regional living conditions were available for a proof-of-concept. This
132 study specifically addressed the following research questions:

- 133 1) How do building density, building type and building height data improve the top-down
134 redistribution of census population at different spatial scales?
- 135 2) How accurate are gridded bottom-up population estimates based on regional living conditions
136 using building density, building type and building height?

137 3) How sensitive are bottom-up estimates to spatially outdated and temporally incomplete data?

138 2. Study Area

139 Our study area is the entirety of Germany. Germany covers an area of about 357,000 km² and had
140 about 82.79 million inhabitants in 2018 [51], with a population density of about 232 inhabitants km⁻².
141 Settlement structure in Germany is highly diverse and characterized by both dense agglomerations and
142 rural structures, with population density ranging from 69 km⁻² to 4,055 km⁻² in its federal states [51]
143 and large urban-rural gradients. This study uses administrative areas from Eurostat NUTS
144 (*Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques*) and LAU (Local Administrative Unit) territorial
145 units [52] as well as Planning Areas for the city of Berlin [53]. Germany (as a NUTS-0 unit) has 16
146 Federal States (among which Berlin, Hamburg and Bremen are city-states) on a NUTS-1 level, 401
147 districts on a NUTS-3 level and 11,267 municipalities on a LAU level. The city of Berlin counts 448
148 planning areas (BPA). The average spatial resolution (ASR), a widely used measure in gridded
149 population mapping and defined as the square root of area divided by the number of administrative
150 units (54,55), is 149.50 km for NUTS-1 units, 29.86 km for NUTS-3 units, 5.63 km for municipalities,
151 and 1.41 km for BPA. We did not consider 38 NUTS-2 level regions, as their scale is similar to
152 NUTS-1 units in some (mostly eastern) and similar to NUTS-3 units in other (mostly western) parts of
153 Germany.

154

155 **Fig 1. Study Area Administrative Units**

156 NUTS (Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques) and LAU (Local Administrative Units) in the study area. LAU
 157 delineations within Berlin correspond to local planning areas, Proj: ETRS-89

158 **3. Data and Methods**

159 This study mapped gridded population using three covariate layers derived from S1 and S2 A/B time
 160 series, as well as from crowd-sourced OSM data. (1) We generated a building density layer based on a
 161 previously established workflow [56] and used (2) a previously generated building height layer [57].
 162 (3) A building type layer was specifically developed for this study. Census population is used as an
 163 input to population redistribution and for validation on different scales, as well as to parameterize the
 164 bottom-up approach.

165 **3.1. Census Data**

166 Population of the study area in 2018 (reference date: 31 Dec 2017) was retrieved from the German
 167 Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy [51]. Those data contain official population counts on a
 168 national level (NUTS-0) as well as for all NUTS-1, NUTS-3 and LAU units. Population counts are
 169 based on continuous updates of the 2011 census [58] and account for natural population change (births

170 and deaths) and net migration (immigration, emigration and sub-national migration, 59). Actual census
171 data from 2011 was used for calibrating the bottom-up estimate. Population counts for BPA (reference
172 date: 01 Jan 2019) were retrieved from the Berlin Senate Department for Urban Development and
173 Housing [53].

174 **3.2. Earth Observation-based Data**

175 **3.2.1. Building Density**

176 We generated a building density layer derived from a S1 and S2 image time series from 2017 and
177 2018 that quantifies the sub-pixel share of impervious surfaces in percent with a spatial resolution of
178 $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^2 = 100 \text{ m}^2$; thus, each percent equals 1 m^2 of impervious surfaces (Fig 2-1A, 60). This
179 imperviousness layer is based on a workflow presented and validated in [61] that used a regression-
180 based unmixing approach and spectral-temporal metrics of S1 and S2 time series. We here expanded
181 on this workflow with an adapted STM feature set (see SI 1A). As population should only be allocated
182 to buildings, we also used crowd-sourced OSM vector data [62] to support the distinction of buildings
183 from other impervious surfaces (Fig 2-1B, see SI 1B). Shares of infrastructure were subtracted from
184 shares of impervious surfaces to yield building density (Fig 2-1C).

185 **3.2.2. Building Height**

186 This study made use of a building height layer with a resolution of $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^2$ (Fig 2-2, 57). This layer
187 represents the average building height within a 50 m radius [63]. It was generated based on spatial
188 spectral-temporal metrics (SSTM) of S1 and S2 time series. SSTMs represent textural information, not
189 only accounting for reflectance and backscatter values of a single grid cell value, but also of the
190 surrounding cells through the use of morphological operators. A radius of 50 m was used to generate
191 SSTMs, based on the assumption that roughness and seasonal shadow effects within that area are
192 robust descriptors of building height [63]. In contrast to the original dataset, building height in this
193 study was not masked with an existing settlement layer.

194

195 **Fig 2. Earth Observation-based covariate layers**

196 (1A) Imperviousness and (1B) infrastructure density from OSM to generate (1C) building density. (2) Building Height.

197 Projection: ETRS-89

198 3.2.3. Building Type Classification

199 We generated information about building types at a spatial resolution of 10 x 10 m² for all cells with a
 200 building density > 25 percent. We classified four different building types – industrial and commercial
 201 (IC), multi-family residential (MF), single-family residential (SF) and lightweight structure (LS)
 202 buildings with a random forest classification approach. IC structures relate to buildings in industrial or
 203 business parks, retail or whole sale commercial centres, but also to other non-residential buildings,
 204 such as stadiums, schools or airports. MF and SF are residential building types mainly distinguished
 205 based on their size, as SF buildings are usually smaller. LS buildings are light structures such as sheds
 206 in allotment gardens or semi-permanent mobile homes. The workflow of building type mapping and
 207 its rationale can be found in SI 2. We achieved an overall classification accuracy of 81.40 percent.

208 3.3. Top-Down Redistribution of Census Population

209 We generated several gridded population maps using a gradient of increasingly complex covariate
 210 layers for redistributing NUTS-0 population from 2018 to the grid-cells (Fig 3).

211 (a) In a first step, we equally redistributed NUTS-0 population to all grid cells that contain a building
 212 (i.e. building density > 25% after the application of the correction factor). In this binary dasymmetric
 213 (BD) mapping approach, all cells hold an equal amount of population. This approach is referred to as

214 BD-BUILD. Binary dasymetric approaches are based on eq. (1), with $pop_{i,j}$ being the population
215 within a grid cell i,j , $inh_{i,j}$ being the binary factor of whether a cell can be inhabited in the current
216 model and pop_{total} being the total NUTS-0 population.

$$217 \quad (1) \quad pop_{i,j} = inh_{i,j} * \frac{pop_{total}}{\sum_{n=0}^{i+j} inh_n}$$

218 (b) In a second step, this procedure was refined by equally redistributing NUTS-0 population to all
219 building cells classified as residential area (MF and SF). This refinement accounted for the fact that *de*
220 *jure* population can usually not be found in non-residential areas. This approach is referred to as BD-
221 RESI.

222 (c) While discrete land cover classification implies that a land cover feature (here: a building) is either
223 present or absent, settlements are highly heterogeneous areas characterized by many objects smaller
224 than the grid cell size or objects split by multiple cells. Thus, we performed a weighted dasymetric
225 (WD) mapping approach using building density as a weight for redistributing NUTS-0 population to
226 residential building cells. This approach is referred to as WD-DENS. Weighted dasymetric approaches
227 are based on eq. (2), with $w_{i,j}$ being the cell weight.

$$228 \quad (2) \quad pop_{i,j} = w_{i,j} * \frac{pop_{total}}{\sum_{n=0}^{i+j} w_n}$$

229 (d) In order to account for vertical structure, building density information was multiplied with building
230 height to obtain cell-based building volume. Here, we use building volume as a weighting factor to
231 redistribute NUTS-0 population to residential building cells. This approach is referred to as WD-VOL.

232 (e) Using building volume for grid-based dasymetric mapping implies that an equal proportion of
233 building area and height can be assigned to each citizen. However, there is a particular difference of
234 living floor area per capita in SF and MF housing and previous research found that incorporating those
235 particularities is beneficial for an accurate population estimate on a local level [64]. We here
236 performed an empirical sensitivity analysis to adjust volume weights of MF residential housing (see SI
237 6). This approach is referred to as WD-VOLADJ.

238

Validation: NUTS-1, NUTS-3, LAU, BPA

239 **Fig 3. Workflow: Top-down redistribution of census population**

240 Workflow of the data-driven redistribution of census data using different dasymetric mapping approaches. BDM: Binary
 241 Dasymetric Mapping. WDM: Weighted Dasymetric Mapping. Refer to text for details about BD-BUILD, BD-RESI, WD-
 242 DENS, WD-VOL, WD-VOLADJ.

243 **3.4. Bottom-up Gridded Population**

244 In this bottom-up approach, we generated gridded population estimates without a-priori knowledge of
 245 the total population count. We used building density, height and type layers that are all physically
 246 related to population (Fig 4).

247 First, building height was used to derive the number of floors of SF and MF buildings per cell. We
 248 reduced building height by 3.00 m to account for roof area where population is not expected.
 249 Buildings lower than 2.00 m were excluded. We assumed a floor height of 4.50 m, based on empirical
 250 work in [64], who found a floor height between 4.00 m and 5.55 m for different building types in a
 251 local setting in South-West Germany. The number of floors was the building height divided by floor
 252 height (as decimal number, but at least 1.00). Living floor area was the number of floors multiplied
 253 with building area per cell, using an adjustment factor of 0.8 that accounted for uninhabitable areas
 254 such as walls or staircases [64]. Finally, living floor area per cell was divided by the average living
 255 floor area per capita (LFA/cap), resulting in the number of people per cell. LFA/cap was derived from
 256 census-based data on a NUTS-1 level providing the number of dwellings in SF and MF buildings and
 257 the average living floor area per dwelling, assuming that household sizes are the same (see SI 5). This
 258 approach is referred to as BU-LFA. As the nature of bottom-up modelling does not enforce an a-priori

259 total, this also allows for a more independent validation compared to top-down population
 260 redistribution.

261
$$(3) \text{ pop}_{i,j} = \frac{\frac{bHeight_{i,j} - rHeight_{i,j}}{fHeight_{i,j}} * bResDens_{i,j} * 0.8}{LFA/cap_{i,j,t,s}}$$

262 Cell values were based on eq. (3), with $bHeight_{i,j}$ being the building height in cell i,j , $rHeight_{i,j}$ being
 263 the roof height, $fHeight_{i,j}$ being the floor height, $bResDens_{i,j}$ being the density of residential buildings
 264 in a cell and $LFA/cap_{i,j,t,s}$ being the living floor area per capita of a cell with building type t in state s .

265
 266 **Fig 4. Workflow: Bottom-up gridded population**

267 Building fraction, building height and floor area per capita for bottom-up mapping. Refer to text for details about BU-LFA.

268 3.5. Spatial and Temporal Bottom-up Mapping Sensitivity

269 Finally, we mapped gridded population using a bottom-up approach based on building density, type
 270 and height, assuming that LFA/cap information is spatially incomplete or temporally outdated. In a
 271 first step, we calculated gridded population using yearly LFA/cap data from 1994 to 2017 and
 272 compared the outcomes to a model using data from 2018, all based on averaged LFA/cap value from
 273 all NUTS-1 areas. In a second step, we calculated gridded population across the whole study area
 274 using LFA/cap information from one NUTS-1 unit respectively and compared each model to the
 275 regionalized model. This second comparison was using LFA/cap information from 2011, as updated
 276 regional data is not available for 2018.

277 **3.6. Quality Assessment**

278 A quantitative quality assessment of gridded population was performed using the established
279 procedure of comparing aggregated gridded population to census reference data at fine spatial scale
280 (e.g. Stevens et al. 2015; Reed et al. 2018; Palacios-Lopez et al. 2019). Previous research found that
281 the ASR ratio of validation units and the census units providing input population has a great impact on
282 quality. A small ratio, i.e. a small offset in spatial scale, generally lead to better results as the
283 compared units are less heterogeneous [7,55,65]. For the top-down approach we compared gridded
284 population to census data on NUTS-1, NUTS-3 and LAU/BPA level. We focused on the smallest
285 available reference unit, which represents the largest possible national-level ASR ratio between input
286 and validation units. Bottom-up results were validated at all scales including NUTS-0. We derived
287 model metrics of uncertainty (root mean squared error RMSE and mean absolute error MAE),
288 coefficient of determination R^2 and model slope.

289 We additionally computed relative quality metrics. These included the mean absolute percentage error
290 (MAPE) that relates the overall MAE to the average population at the respective scale, and the relative
291 estimation error (REE) that describes the mean error of population reference and estimate in each unit
292 relative to its reference population (e.g. 42). Models were also evaluated regarding REE in relation to
293 actual census population density and spatial resolution in order to examine if additional covariate
294 layers can equally improve population estimates in both smaller and larger areas with both high and
295 low population density. For this purpose, we also analysed the distribution of LAU validation units
296 and population counts within different ranges of REE (0 - 10 %, 10 – 25 %, 25 – 50 %, 50 – 100 %, >
297 100 % over- and underestimation).

298 **4. Results**

299 **4.1. Top-Down Redistribution of Census Population**

300 Population results can be compared along two dimensions – the applied (re-)distribution method (Fig 5,
301 rows) and the scale of validation (Fig 5, columns). We found that in dasymetric mapping approaches
302 (BD-BUILD to WD-VOLADJ) overall results improved along both dimensions. At all validation
303 scales, limiting built-up areas to residential building types only is preferable, while improvements

304 were larger on a finer validation scale. For example, MAPE decreased from 152.73% to 68.64% at
 305 BAP level, from 53.08% to 49.50% at LAU level and from 20.45% to 19.73% on a NUTS-1 level.
 306 Similar improvements could be observed for MAE, RMSE, R^2 and Slope. Using building density,
 307 quality metrics improved slightly across all scales. The level of model quality increased markedly
 308 when building height was introduced. MAE decreased from 4,100 to 2,600 at BAP-level, from 2,100
 309 to 1,400 at LAU-level and from 52,700 to 34,600 at NUTS-3-level. MAPE, RMSE, Slope and R^2
 310 improved accordingly. At a NUTS-1-level, the increase in quality was less pronounced, but still
 311 visible regarding MAPE, MAE or RMSE. Including an adjusted building volume, quality metrics
 312 improved at a NUTS-1- and NUTS-3-level, while stagnating or slightly declining at LAU- and BAP-
 313 level. We here present the results for an approach that adjusts volume weights of MF residential
 314 housing by a factor of 1.6, based on a comparison of different weighting factors. Using binary
 315 covariate layers, NUTS-1-level results largely outmatched those at finer scale units with regard to
 316 MAPE, slope and R^2 . Upon integration of building density and volume, NUTS-3- and LAU-level
 317 quality approached that of NUTS-1 with regard to slope and R^2 . While Fig 5 provides a visual
 318 representation of major quality metrics, SI 8 provides precise numbers and scatterplots.

319

320

321 **Fig 5. Top-down and bottom-up gridded population mapping quality**

322 Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), Slope and R^2 of redistribution models at different spatial validation scales (NUTS-1
 323 to LAU and BPA). All numbers used to create this figure in SI 8.

324 Using building volume reduced both the underestimation of population counts in areas with high
 325 population density and the overestimation in areas with comparatively low population density (Fig 6,
 326 top). The distribution of REE values of all validation units (NUTS-1 to LAU) showed that absolute
 327 distribution skewness decreases after integrating building density and volume, and that negative and
 328 positive REE became less related to population density. The relation of REE to spatial resolution was
 329 not as pronounced as that between REE and population density (Fig 6, bottom). However, results also
 330 improved in BD-RESI and WD-VOLADJ, where mean REE values were closer to zero and standard
 331 deviations decreased compared to the previous model.

332
 333 **Fig 6. Population mapping quality in relation to population density and spatial resolution**

334 Population density (top) and spatial resolution (bottom) of all NUTS-1, NUTS-3 and LAU areas related to their respective
 335 relative estimation error (REE) in the different redistribution models. Black dots: Mean value of y-axis bins. Grey bars: Mean
 336 values of bins +/- one standard deviation. |skew|= absolute skewness of the means.

337 Different population models showed a different distribution of LAU (Fig 7, left) and of reference
 338 population (Fig 7, right) within REE ranges. In BD-BUILD, for example, 154 LAU units had an REE
 339 of -100 to -50 %, 989 units had an REE of -50 to -25 %, 1,249 units had an REE of -25 to -10 %, etc.
 340 Correspondingly, for example, 8.3 million people are living in areas where BD-BUILD showed an
 341 REE of -10 to 0 %. In BD-BUILD, BD-RESI and WD-DENS, only a small number of LAU showed
 342 population underestimation. In a volume-preserving approach, this resulted in a rather large number
 343 with positive REE values, as overall population estimates remain stable by definition. Results

344 suggested that the integration of building volume helps to balance the number of LAU in which
 345 population is under- or overestimated. Compared to WD-DENS, the number of LAU with an REE
 346 between -25% and +25% increased from about 4,600 to 5,700. Similar patterns could be observed in
 347 the distribution of population. Here, the use of building volume leads to an important increase of
 348 population in areas that were modeled rather accurately, i.e. with REE values between -25 and +25%
 349 (about 58,827,000 with 25,972,000 people in areas modeled with REE between -10 and +10 %)
 350 compared to using building density only (40,801,000 with 16,776,000 between -10 and +10 %).

351

352 **Fig 7. Distribution of Local Administrative Units and reference population by error range**

353 Histogram of LAU validation units (left) and census reference population (right) within REE bins for each model. Orange
 354 colors represent underestimation, purple colors represent overestimation, grey color represents accurate predictions (REE
 355 ranges from -10% to +10%). All numbers used to create this figure in SI 7.

356 In BD-BUILD, BD-RESI and WD-DENS, relatively few LAU had negative REE (Fig 7). A spatial
 357 representation of REE at LAU level confirmed that population tended to be underestimated in and
 358 around agglomerations, i.e. LAU with a comparatively high population density (Fig 8). Integrating
 359 building volume in WD-VOL and WD-VOLADJ reduced differences between urban agglomerations
 360 and surrounding rural areas. Also, regional differences in REE became smaller. The number of highly
 361 over- and underestimated regions was reduced, and only few LAU remained where a large REE met
 362 high population proportions, for example in the very west of Germany.

363

364 **Fig 8. Quality of gridded population models by LAU (spatial representation)**

365 Spatial distribution of REE by LAU and model. Purple shades imply over-estimation, orange shades imply under-estimation,
 366 grey shades imply accurate predictions (REE between -10% and +10%).

367 **4.2. Bottom-up Gridded Population**

368 Quality metrics of the bottom-up approach matched those of WD-VOL and WD-VOLADJ, with
 369 slightly lower MAE and RMSE at NUTS-1- and NUTS-3-level (Fig 5). This also applied to the
 370 relation of REE to actual population density and spatial resolution, with the exception of a slight
 371 underestimation of validation units with a population density of up to about 1,000 km², also resulting
 372 in a higher absolute distribution skewness (Fig 6). The use of BU-LFA showed a similar distribution
 373 to WD-VOLADJ with regard to the number of LAU and census population in different REE ranges,
 374 with a slightly higher number of LAU where population is underestimated (Fig 7). Accordingly, BU-
 375 LFA results were very similar to WD-VOLADJ with regard to the spatial patterns of quality, with
 376 some local particularities, for example a slightly higher population estimation in northern central
 377 Germany (Fig 8).

378 **4.3 Spatial and Temporal Bottom-up Mapping Sensitivity**

379 Including LFA/cap estimates from a different spatial or temporal context in the BU-LFA models
 380 showed that using data from previous years can yield good results (Fig 9, left). LFA/cap from 2012 to
 381 2017 did not substantially alter the estimated population at the national or LAU level. LAU population
 382 using LFA/cap data from 2012 was overestimated by about 1 % compared to using LFA/cap data from
 383 2018. Using data from 2010 and 2011, overestimations became slightly higher, with a low variance of
 384 population overestimation. Until 2009, overestimations were much higher, as smaller LFA/cap from
 385 before that year were used together with higher built-up surface density from 2018. Using LFA/cap
 386 data from 2018, overall population was estimated to be 78.84 million, as compared to a census
 387 reference of 82.8 million inhabitants.

388 Fig 9 (right) shows population estimates across the whole study area on a NUTS-0 (blue line) and
 389 LAU level (boxplots), assuming that LFA/cap data is only available for a spatial subset. We see that
 390 compared to the regionalized model (reg.), which used individual LFA/cap data per federal state, LAU
 391 population showed an under-/overestimation factor of 0.85 to 1.15 when using regional data only. This
 392 is also discernible in the overall population estimates, which ranged from about 74.5 million
 393 inhabitants when data from Saarland (SL) is used to about 84.9 million when data from Brandenburg
 394 (BB) is used. Using regionalized LFA/cap data from 2011, overall population is estimated to be 78.5
 395 million.

396

397 **Fig 9. Quality of bottom-up gridded population mapping using floor area per capita from a different**
 398 **subset**

399 (Left) Ratio of population estimates within all LAU when using LFA/cap (national average) from different years compared to
400 LFA/cap from 2018. Blue line: Predicted Population Total. (Right) Ratio of population estimates within all LAU when using
401 LFA/cap from a single NUTS-1 unit for the whole study area only compared to individual LFA/cap per NUTS-1 unit. Blue
402 line: Predicted Population Total.

403 **5. Discussion**

404 **5.1. Earth Observation-based Data**

405 The quality of gridded population estimates is directly related to the availability and quality of the
406 underlying covariate layers as well as the temporal and semantic consistency between census data and
407 ancillary datasets. An increased amount of suitable ancillary datasets increases mapping uncertainties
408 [7]. We here used previously established top-down dasymetric and bottom-up mapping approaches
409 and combined them with a previously unused set of covariate layers that are directly and physically
410 related to population.

411 A building density layer was created based on an established workflow to map imperviousness, but
412 using an adapted training feature set. An extensive discussion of the workflow including possible
413 methodological challenges can be found in the corresponding study [56]. The major challenges of
414 using rasterized OSM data for the distinction of building and impervious non-building surfaces are
415 discussed in the corresponding supplementary material (SI 1B). An extensive discussion of the
416 previously generated building height layer can be found in the corresponding study [63]. A building
417 type layer was specifically created for this study. A more detailed discussion of this mapping approach
418 can be found in the corresponding supplementary material (SI 2).

419 **5.2. Top-Down Redistribution of Census Population**

420 In dasymetric mapping, census data determines the initial population to be redistributed. Low quality
421 or outdated census data bears the risk of erroneously misjudging dasymetric mapping results as
422 redistribution and validation are based on the same dataset. We used national census data for Germany
423 from 2018, which is based on yearly updates of the 2011 census.

424 BD-BUILD used a binary building layer to redistribute population. Here, population in a large number
425 of LAU was overestimated. However, the majority of census population lived in LAU where

426 population was underestimated and the distribution of REE related to population density showed a
427 rather high skewness (Fig 6). The spatial representation of results confirmed that the population of
428 urban agglomerations tended to be underestimated, resulting in an overestimation of many less
429 populated LAU. BD-RESI excluded cells with non-residential buildings. Results improved most at
430 finer scale, possibly because here the shares of residential and non-residential buildings are more
431 heterogeneous across the validation units. This shows that building type information is particularly
432 helpful to identify local population patterns. WD-DENS accounted for building density and improved
433 overall mapping quality. This is generally in line with findings from [42]. Particularly, the share of
434 people living in highly underestimated LAU was reduced and the REE distribution skewness
435 decreased. This is because WD-DENS factors in higher building density in urban areas compared to
436 lower building density in rural areas, whereas BD-RESI did not distinguish those regional
437 particularities. WD-VOL introduced building volume as a weighting layer. Building volume largely
438 improved quality across all validation scales, for example by reducing RMSE by about 50 percent
439 compared to WD-DENS at NUTS-3 and LAU level. A remarkably larger portion of census population
440 was predicted to live in areas where estimates were accurate. Volume increased model quality because
441 population density in cells with an equal building density is further modulated through vertical
442 building differentiation. These findings, supported by the spatial representation of results, suggest that
443 differences in quality between densely settled agglomerations and sparsely settled areas, an issue also
444 reported in other studies [7,42,47], are overcome by introducing volume. While it was shown that
445 highly accurate 3D building models are beneficial for population mapping [45], this has not yet been
446 proven to function with potentially globally available Earth Observation products, also because those
447 are just recently emerging [63,66]. A volume adjustment factor further improved quality at a fine scale
448 and the number of LAU where population is over- or underestimated became more balanced. A
449 regionalized factor could possibly be beneficial, but would also increase the unwanted correlation of
450 input census and validation data. Quality still showed regional patterns: For example, population in
451 North-Western Germany, Northern Bavaria and parts of Eastern Germany tended to be overestimated,
452 whereas population in Southern Germany and Northern Germany tended to be underestimated. In this
453 respect, it seems that the covariate layers did not entirely represent regional heterogeneity.

454 Nevertheless, compared to the other models, a larger share of the census population lived in accurately
455 predicted areas. Results showed that it is generally beneficial to account for different living conditions
456 in different building types.

457 **5.3. Bottom-up Gridded Population**

458 In bottom-up mapping, census data provide information about local living conditions. Regional data
459 on living floor area were only available for 2011, which could, for example, explain the
460 underestimation of total population when regionalized data from 2011 was used in comparison to
461 census data from spatial subsets to estimate total population (Fig 9, right). Bottom-up gridded
462 population mapping was shown to be useful when national census data is outdated or spatially
463 incomplete, or when living conditions across the study area are heterogeneous. However, it can still be
464 challenging, because it requires local survey data that is relatable to the available covariate data [49].
465 Using layers with a direct and physical relation to population, a nation-wide bottom-up population
466 estimate can be created with high accuracy. The quality of BU-LFA were comparable to the top-down
467 approaches WD-VOL and WD-VOLADJ and spatial patterns were highly similar. Total population
468 was estimated to be 78.5 million, which is an underestimation of 5.7 % compared to census population.
469 The required additional input is limited to assumptions about average LFA/cap and housing
470 characteristics such as floor and roof height. Those are a potential source of error, as spatial and
471 thematic granularity of input data (e.g. detail of differentiation for SF and MF housing) might be
472 driving regional quality.

473 **5.4. Spatial Scale**

474 Scale is a particular subject of interest in gridded population mapping and can be discussed along two
475 dimensions: 1) the minimum mapping unit and its suitability for a specific application and 2) the
476 aggregation scale of the gridded data for validation purposes. Cell size is inherently depending on the
477 spatial resolution of covariate layers. Here, we used an original spatial resolution of 10m for all
478 covariates, based on the native resolution of the Earth Observation data. This is an advantage
479 compared to large area products commonly available at a 100m resolution or coarser, as high-
480 resolution maps make it possible to describe local patterns with high detail. However, high resolution

481 results are affected by the OSM correction factor, leading to reliable absolute population counts
482 starting from about 100 m minimum mapping unit, which was also found to be sufficient for many
483 analyses starting at a neighborhood level [7].

484 The validation of dasymetric approaches is not entirely independent, as population to be redistributed
485 and gridded data usually originate from the same census. While it illustrates whether the redistribution
486 produced accurate spatial patterns, no conclusion about actual population counts can be drawn. The
487 most accurate gridded population maps can be produced using a small offset in scale between input
488 providing the census population to be redistributed and validation units [42]. An indicator for this
489 offset is the ASR ratio, the ASR relation of input and validation units. Knowing that census data might
490 sometimes only be available on a national level, it is desirable to achieve high accuracies at high ASR
491 ratios, which is also a sign of suitable ancillary data across heterogeneous areas (Leyk et al. 2019). It is,
492 thus, necessary that the quality of gridded population is always related to this offset in scale, also
493 because some quality metrics referring to absolute population (e.g. MAE) are not comparable across
494 studies otherwise.

495 In this study, we redistributed NUTS-0 census data to a 10m grid, which was then validated on an
496 aggregated NUTS-1, NUTS-3, LAU and, locally, BPA level. The ASR ratio was 106.2 at LAU level,
497 20.0 at NUTS-3 level and 3.9 between at NUTS-1 level. Datasets where gridded population was
498 modeled with WD-VOLADJ and BU-LFA by redistributing LAU population in order to create the
499 most accurate maps possible will be made openly available once the manuscript is accepted for
500 publication and can be explored in an interactive map viewer: [https://ows.geo.hu-](https://ows.geo.hu-berlin.de/webviewer/population)
501 [berlin.de/webviewer/population](https://ows.geo.hu-berlin.de/webviewer/population). We found that besides the fact that overall quality metrics increased
502 with decreasing ASR ratio for nearly any model, the impact of enhanced covariate layers including
503 building density, type and height on quality becomes more apparent at higher ASR ratios. While
504 overall quality metrics across all validation units are important, it is also desirable that the quality
505 within the individual units is acceptable for a given application. The integration of (adjusted) volume
506 contributed considerably to decoupling REE from the size and population density of the validation unit
507 (Fig 6).

508 **5.5. Spatial and Temporal Transferability**

509 Temporal transferability of gridded population models becomes relevant if no census data is available
510 for the point in time to be mapped, which may rather be the rule than the exception. As dasymetric
511 mapping approaches are volume-preserving, model transfer is more interesting in bottom-up
512 approaches, where the suitability of LFA/cap data from a different point in time can be tested. While
513 always depending on local conditions, related results are an indicator for overall temporal model
514 robustness. We found that bottom-up estimates were relatively stable when using LFA/cap from 2010
515 to 2018. This is because before 2010, building statistics were extrapolated from the 1987 census in
516 West Germany and the 1995 building census in East Germany [67]. Since 2010, LFA/cap was
517 extrapolated from the 2011 census, and some of the earlier estimates were corrected according to the
518 new data: For example, the estimated number of SF and MF units was reduced by about 900.000 from
519 2009 to 2010 with an increasing total living floor area, leading to a jump in LFA/cap statistics.
520 Population before 2010 was overestimated, because lower LFA/cap statistics at this time are now used
521 together with higher building volume.

522 Spatial transferability of gridded population models becomes relevant if no area-wide census is
523 available. We therefore tested the quality of bottom-up population estimates if LFA/cap was available
524 from a subregion only. Note that the results considering spatial and temporal transferability are not
525 comparable among each other, as regional LFA/cap on a NUTS-1 level could only be derived for 2011
526 and with a slightly different approach than historic LFA/cap (see SI 5). We mapped nation-wide
527 population using LFA/cap from one selected NUTS-1 region at a time and compared the results to
528 using a regionalized model (i.e. as in BU-LFA). Population is over- or underestimated by up to ca.
529 10%, depending on the region that contributed LFA/cap. Thus, results showed that data from a
530 subregion can generally be used for bottom-up mapping as long as local living conditions are largely
531 stable or within a fairly low margin of change, which is in line with findings of a similar study in Haiti
532 [40]. However, the representativity of the region providing LFA/cap can have an impact on mapping
533 results. LFA/cap from Mecklenburg-West Pomerania, featuring the lowest population density in
534 Germany, led to a large quality range and fewer LAU were accurately mapped compared to using
535 LFA/cap from North Rhine-Westphalia, which itself hosts nearly a fifth of the total population.

536 **6. Conclusion**

537 We mapped gridded population across Germany to quantify how mapping quality relates to input
538 covariate data that is directly and physically related to population. We found that an equal weighting
539 of building cells along the urban-rural gradient and, thus, an equal distribution of population seems
540 inadequate. While building density and building type were found to be useful for dasymetric mapping,
541 particularly with regard to local analyses, building height improved mapping most remarkably and at
542 all spatial scales and contributed to a more spatially equal distribution of mapping quality. Foremost,
543 building height reduced the underestimation of population in dense urban environments and
544 particularly increased result quality when the average spatial resolution ratio was high, which indicates
545 that height enables accurate population maps without high-resolution census reference data.

546 Our approach including building height allows for creating a fine-scale picture of population
547 distribution from both top-down and bottom-up mapping. Building height improves mapping quality
548 across large areas and, in particular, accurately describes population heterogeneity along urban-rural
549 gradients, i.e. in areas with both higher and lower population density. This is advantageous compared
550 to products that use two-dimensional information only, such as GHS-POP. We also see this approach
551 advantageous compared to approaches with a higher modeling effort, for example WorldPop products
552 or LandScan, where the relation of covariate layers to population is a-priori unknown and region-
553 specific. It is potentially transferable globally, as covariate layers are based on freely, globally
554 available and consistently pre-processed satellite imagery and as it features consistent semantics.

555 We are accordingly convinced that this study provides a valuable contribution towards more robust
556 and accurate fine-scale gridded population mapping and suggest to make the effort to implement
557 building type and, even though not yet consistently available across the globe, building height data
558 into existing gridded population products. We underline the importance of providing population
559 mapping accuracy related to the scale of validation and of using relative quality metrics. More
560 accurate fine scale population maps will contribute to a deeper understanding of processes relevant for
561 global and climate change mitigation, to efforts in mapping social-environmental key variables such as

562 material stocks, as well as to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, both in specific
563 regions of interest, but also globally along urban-rural gradients.

564 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

565 None.

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